

WORKERS' AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT AND THE ROLE OF MANAGERS' INGRATIATION IN TOURISM-BASED ORGANIZATIONS

Chukwuma, Emeka Adiele

Department of Hospitality Management and Tourism, Faculty of Management Sciences, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

Abstract: *This paper examined the impact of managers' ingratiation on workers' affective commitment in tourism related business organizations in Port Harcourt. The paper adopted a cross-sectional survey research design, involving a population of 170 workers. The research data were collected through questionnaire and analyzed using Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient (rs). It was found that managers' ingratiation has become a referent power factor which managers in the tourism sector have used to elicit and sustain workers affective commitment. The paper concludes that managers' flattery behavior to appear likeable is a strong affective commitment factor in the workplace. Based on this, the paper recommends that managers should build on their referent power to enhance their charismatic capital necessary to engender workers' emotional and selfless interest, dedication to job, sense of belongingness and civic virtue.*

Keywords: *manager's ingratiation, affective commitment, downward impression management, upward impression management and organizational commitment*

Introduction

The increasing attention on workers' commitment has shown that organizational effectiveness and efficiency largely depend on the extent to which the workers are committed. Some previous studies attempted to examine how monetary based motivation engenders workers' commitment. This is evident in the works of (Morrison, 2007; Rungruang and Tangchitnob, 2010 and Emmanuel, 2012), where the point is proven beyond researchable doubt that, where the prevailing workers' needs are physiological, money tends to elicit commitment. Also, Asawo (2009) conducted a study on spirituality at work and workers' commitment and found that, leadership spiritual context

is strongly associated with the level of followers' commitment in the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Also, Rousseau and Aube (2010) examined the antecedents of organizational commitment to find out if both supervisor and co-worker support relate positively to employees' effective commitment in organization. They concluded that, based on the benefits accruable to both the individual and the organizations, managers may want to take steps to strengthen the employees' affective commitment to the organization. They further argued that since employees have the tendency to engage in continuing

interaction with the immediate supervisors and co-workers, such social interactions in the workplace will most likely influence employees work experience.

This is similar to the study by Okaomme (2011) where the relationship between leaders' emotional intelligence and workers' affective commitment was investigated. In that study, it was found that leaders' emotional intelligence provides strong extrinsic influence on workers' affective commitment, positively.

However, with the rapid growth in the Nigerian tourism sector, with its attendant pressure on both managers and workers, the need for affective commitment is high, yet research in this area is lacking. Whereas, the dominant research perspectives bear economic and psychological antecedents, the social antecedents are lacking any empirical support. This gap in knowledge on affective commitment from a social perspective formed our point of departure. In this study, our point of departure therefore, is to use one identify social action phenomena – ingratiatio, 'to explain the dynamics in workers' affective commitment in the tourism-based businesses in Nigeria.

In this context, ingratiatio has been used to connote managers disposition to apply flattery, self-presentation, self-construction, inspiring words and incentive value to attract a public image before the subordinates. Affective commitment is used to demonstrate the worker emotional attachment to issues relating to the job. Such affects one self-interest, dedication to job, sense of belonging and civic virtue. Selfless interest manifest in sacrificing personal comfort for the organization sake; sense of belonging is the feeling of one been integrated with the organization and the unwillingness see other opportunities outside; dedication to job is seen in terms of attention one gives to his duty; and civic virtue represents the worker's concern for the welfare of others and safety of public infrastructure by doing the right thing. **The Concept and Nature of Impression management**

Daggs (2008) (in Lim and Sambrook 2010) acknowledged that the concept of impression management was initially introduced by Goffman (in Carno, 2000) who approached the presentation of self as a performance. In daily interactions, Goffman believed that people would make conscious decisions about the appropriate role to play or the appropriate part of themselves to display in interactions. According to Goffman (in Carno, 2000), actors also constantly manipulate their behaviour, because they are always aware of the way that their behaviour can be interpreted and the way others can view them. Their relationships with others in the interaction can be important also in determining the facet of their identity they wish to portray. Mets and Caldwell and O'Reilly (2003) summarized impression management and self-presentation by stating, –Self-presentation refers to the process by which individuals, more or less intentionally, construct a public self that is likely to elicit certain types of attributions from others, attributions that would facilitate the achievement of some goals, usually to acquire social rewards or advantages, or to prevent loss of self-esteem when future failure seems probable. The concept of carefully communicating information about ourselves and managing the information others receive about us has inspired a significant amount of work in the area of social psychology. For instance, Jones and Pittman (2009) who were leaders in conducting experimental research focused on impression management or self-presentation, defined self-presentation as, –an actor's shaping of his or her responses to create an impression that is for one reason or another desired by the actor. In some ways, impression management could be viewed as strategic self-disclosure, as individuals make careful considerations about what information, they should share about themselves

in specific contexts, based on the audience present and the goals that the individual has in interacting with the other persons.

Similarly, Liden and Mitchell (2010) argued that, the term –impression management is usually used interchangeably with –self-presentation. Self-presentation as conceptualized here builds on Goffman's (in Carno, 2000) theories of identity and social performance. Goffman's thesis states that self-presentation is the intentional and tangible component of identity. Social actors engage in complex intra-self-negotiations to project a desired impression. This impression is maintained through consistently performing coherent and complementary behaviours. Liden and Mitchell (2010) called this process impression management. Impression management therefore, refers to the process of influencing the impressions an audience form about oneself. Other people's perceptions of us play a significant role in our lives; they influence our relationship, shaping the rewards we receive. Liden and Mitchell (2010) further stated that virtually everyone thinks about other people's impressions of him or her from time to time and some people worry a great deal about how others regard them. Thus, our daily behaviour is more or less, deeply influenced by impression management. Impression management holds various applications in social behaviour, as well as many factors that have been hypothesized to relate to it. Chenjing (in Liden and Mitchell, 2010) also conceptualized a model to explain the motivation and style that people manage their public image. The three-stage model introduced has two components considered in the integrated impression management process: impression motivation and impression construction, and they are discrete but interrelated. O'Sullivan (2004) developed an impression management model to outline the functional and strategic role of communication choice in social relationships. Chenjing from Mnookin study of online impression management in her online community study stated that impression _need not in any way correspond to a person's real life identity; people can make and remake themselves, choosing their gender and the details of their online presentation. He observed that researchers also believe that certain social and material goals push people to manage impression in the real world, such as securing a job at an interview or attracting someone enough to get a date, development of identity and maintenance of self-esteem. While in the online world, researchers have examined the online impression management motivation to include a desire to build up relationships, express unexplored parts of identity or aspects that are inhibited in face-to-face interactions. Thus, people are driven more by this desire to develop identity than a wish to deceive or manipulate. And these goals appear to be self-knowledge. The high degree of freedom in online community gives users the opportunities of alternative presentations. Further studies reported that misrepresentations were more likely online than offline and were most often related to physical appearance and age. Some of the scholars noted that impression management online offered opportunities to present highly desirable self-image and provided a chance for wish-fulfillment. Studies have shown that people, who have social anxiety in real life, will be more likely to manage their desirable impression online to make up for their dissatisfied impression in offline world (Sartain and Shuman, 2006; McGee and Ford, 2009; and Abelson, 2010).

It is demonstrated that the focus of impression management may take one of three forms at any given time. These are: **Upward Impression Management:** Impression management directed at someone higher in the hierarchy. **Downward Impression Management:** Impression management directed at subordinates. **Lateral Impression Management:** Impression management directed at peers (Amaral and Uzzi, 2007).

Ingratiation

The first strategy in impression management is ingratiation, which can be shown when the individual is driven by the concern that others like him or her. Ingratiation is the most theoretically developed of the strategies identified by Jones and Pittman (2009). Ingratiation strategies can be driven by a number of goals and motivations, but is largely determined by the time, the place, and the nature of the relationship. For example, if the self-presenter is of higher status than his or her target, then he or she may use flattery as a strategy. Ingratiation is also driven by three major attraction seeking behaviours. The first is incentive value or why would it be important for the communicator to be liked by the particular target? Power is also an important determinant of incentive value. If the target has some sort of incentive power over the self-presenter, then there is more reason for the self-presenter to insure liking from the target. Subjective probability is the second of the three determinants. Basically, subjective probability is the likelihood that a particular strategy will be successful on the intended target. This is especially important, because if the strategy backfires on the self-presenter, there could be significant implications for the self-presenter, based on whether or not the target has power over the self-presenter. The final of the three determinants is perceived legitimacy. Perceived legitimacy is related to the consistency of the self-presenter's strategies with his or her true self and how appropriate the strategies used **is** given the specific situation. If likeability was the goal of the self-presenter, ingratiation strategies are likely to be used (Arkin and Shepherd, 2010).

Affective Commitment

Affective commitment is of the measure of organizational commitment which represents the individual's emotional attachment to the organization and its goals. According to Meyer and Allen (1997, p.11) affective commitment is –the employee's emotional attachment to identification with, and involvement in the organization. Organizational members who are committed to an organization on an affective basis, continue working for the organization because they want to (Meyer & Allen, 1991). Members who are committed on an effective level stay with the organization because they view their personal employment relationship as congruent to the goals and values of the organization (Beck & Wilson, 2000).

Affective commitment is a work-related attitude with positive feelings towards the organization (Morrow, 1993). Sheldon (1971, p.148) also maintains that this type of attitude is –an orientation towards the organization, which links or attaches the identity of the person to the organization.

Affective commitment is the relative strength of an individual's identification with and involvement in a particular organization (Mowday et al, 1982).

The strength of affective organizational commitment is influenced by the extent to which the individual's needs and expectations about the organization are matched by their actual experience (Storey, 1995). Tetrick (1995, p.589) also describes affective commitment as –value rationality-based organizational commitment which refers to the degree of value congruence between an organizational member and an organization.

Affective commitment has received much attention in literature due to its association with many work outcomes (Rungruang and Tangchitnob, 2010) including absenteeism, job performance, organizational citizenship behaviour labour turnover (Meyer and Mien in Rungruang and Tangchitnob, 2010), job involvement (Biswas, 2009), and turnover intention (Meyer et al. (2002). Its antecedents have been shown to include: job characteristics, organizational dependability, perceived participatory

management (Baridam and Nwibere, 2008); human resource practices (Chai-Amonphaisal and Ussahawanitchakit, 2008); organizational support, role ambiguity, role conflict (Rungruang and Tangchitnob, 2010); distributive justice, procedural justice (Rungruang and Tangchitnob, 2010; Chai-Amonphaisal and Ussahawanitchakit, 2008); immediate supervisor and coworker support (Rousseau and Aubé, 2010); personal characteristics, structural characteristics and work experience (Mowday et al. in Ali et., 2010); leadership justice (Duan et al., 2010); role overload and role conflict (Malik, Waheed and Malik, 2010), psychological climate (Biswas, 2009), supervisory behavior and organizational structure (Agarwal and Ragaswami (1993).

Baridam and Nwibere (2008) identified the antecedents of affective commitment which include: job characteristics (comprising task autonomy, task significance, task identity, skill variety, supervisory feedback); organizational dependability which is the extent to which employees feel that they can count on their organization to take care of their interests; and perceived participatory management, which means the extent to which employees feel they can influence decisions on work-related issues and matters that concern them. This corresponds with Robins (2000) disposition that, task autonomy is the extent to which the employee has freedom, independence and exercise discretion in carrying out a job. Task significance is about the meaningfulness of the job and refers to the extent to which a job is perceived to make significant impact on others and contribute to the organization. Task identity means the extent to which a job brings about completion of a whole, identifiable piece of work, with a visible outcome. Skill variety is the extent to which the job requires the employee to engage diverse activities and utilize different skills and abilities in performing the job. Supervisory feedback refers to the opportunity the job affords employees to be given direct and clear feedback on their task performance. Rungruang and Tangchitnob (2010) equally examined the importance of the antecedents of affective commitment proposed by Meyer and associates (Meyer and Allen, 1991/1997, Meyer et al., 2002), among employees in Thailand. Their aim was to provide a clearer understanding of affective commitment within the context of its work antecedents in Thailand. These antecedents include organizational support (employees perception of the extent to which the organization values their contributions and also cares about their well-being), distributive justice - fairness in distribution of rewards (Chai-Amonphaisal and Ussahawanitchakit, 2008), procedural justice - fairness of the formal procedures by which the distribution of rewards are determined (ChaiAmonphaisal and Ussahawanitchakit, 2008), role ambiguity (clarity of roles and predictability of its outcomes), and role conflict (congruency-incongruency between the requirements of the role and its contribution to organizational goals). The authors found that employees that perceived strong organizational support exhibits stronger emotional attachment (affective commitment) to their organization than others who do not; employee who perceived that the rewards were fair, have higher affective commitment than those who perceive the distribution of rewards were unfair; employees who could not determine what was expected in their role and who perceived incompatibility in the requirements of their role and its contribution to organizational goals exhibited low levels of emotional attachment to their organization. Procedural justice was not a significant predictor of affective commitment. The authors suggest that a possible cause may be due to indirect effect of variables not included in their study such as satisfaction with supervisor. DeConinck and Stilwell's in Rungruang and Tangchitnob (2010) found that employees who perceived that the rewards they received were fair, were more satisfied with their supervisor, which consequently increased their affective commitment. This implies that, task significance aspect of job

characteristics relates to role conflict, while organizational dependability also relates to aspect of organization support.

In a similar study, Chai-Amo'nphaisal and Ussahawanitchakit (2008) investigated the roles of human resource practices (training opportunities, performance appraisal, and career development) and organizational justice (distributive justice and procedural justice) in affective commitment and job performance of accountants in Thailand. They found that: human resource practices have significant positive relationship with affective commitment; organizational justice is positively related to affective commitment; and affective commitment is a strong predictor of job performance. This follows the view of Koys in Chai-Amonphaisal and Ussahawanitchakit (2008) that commitment of employees to their organization relates to their belief that the human resource practices in their organization were geared towards attracting and retaining good employees and in giving fair treatment to the employees. Hence, when organizations seek to increase their employee commitment of their employees via human resource management practices, they are most likely seeking to increase the affective or normative commitment, and not continuance commitment (Meyer and Smith in Chai-Amonphaisal and Ussahawanitchakit (2008). A variation of this finding is reported by Zorlu (2010), that development of employees relates positively with affective and continuance commitment. The author posits that concerning human resource practices, developing employees, is the most vital factor that has a positive influence on organizational commitment, and also noted that the employees and their knowledge, skills and capabilities are extremely important.

In their own research, Lu, Siu and Lu (2010) investigated the role of affective organizational commitment in the Greater China Region. Specifically, they explored the effects that work stressors (heavy workload, interpersonal conflict and lack of autonomy) and affective organizational commitment which is similar to the Chinese value of loyalty to the group, would have on job satisfaction of employees in that region. The authors note that emphasis on group loyalty which is characteristic of the Chinese culture results in employees strongly identifying with the values and goals of the organization, devoting to their job and willingly serving the organization. They purport that loyalty to the organization may enable workers to maintain emotional attachment and exert more efforts during stressful times, noting that paying back is the Chinese value of loyalty. Hence, the Chinese employer guarantees jobs and livelihood; and the employees use their devotion and continued service to pay back. In difficult times also, the employer refrains from laying-off employees and these employees increase their work efforts and unwavering loyalty, by way of paying back. The result is that, for the Chinese workforce, affective commitment produces workers who are devoted and responsible, and who by implication who double their work efforts, especially in peak times of stress. The authors, therefore, based on the premise that affective commitment relates to organizational outcomes more strongly than normative and continuance commitment (Dunham, Grube, & Castafieda in Lu, Siu and Lu, 2010), tested the protective effects of affective commitment on work attitude, and its moderating effects on the work stressors - job satisfaction relationship. Findings of their research revealed that affective commitment had a strong positive relation with job satisfaction, and mediated between two work stressors (interpersonal conflict and lack of autonomy) to determine job satisfaction.

Managers' Ingratiation and Workers' Affective Commitment

The conceptual framework of this study is based on the perception that ingratiation is a social action desiring a reciprocal action. Therefore, in the context of downward impression management, the

purposive intention by managers in engaging in flattery behaviour on the workers may be aimed at the latter's emotional attachment to work relate factors. Emmanuel (2012), in a study on organizational commitment in Nigerian banks, corroborates Arkin and Shepherd's argument that the implication of workplace ingratiation is the fact that ingratiation is driven by three major attraction seeking behaviours. This involved incentive value, subjective probability, and perceived legitimacy. The tendency that the target is trapped by the self-presenter means that likeability will be achieved and affective influences may be enthroned at the workplace.

In downward impression management, the superior employs likeability strategies including referent power and flattery to enhance his charismatic worth (Emmanuel, 2012). These elements are all social action related, which are conducted to induce a positive reciprocal action. However, since the managers, primary goal is to elicit workers' commitment to organizational goals (Robins and Sanghi, 2006; and Okaomee, 2011), it is viewed that ingratiation is a means, therefore implying a goal directed behavior to induce workers commitment beyond obligatory requirement or pecuniary cost-benefit calculations. Based on this, we developed our research concept, from which our operational conceptual framework and research hypotheses were drawn.

Methodology

This correlational study was conducted as a cross-sectional survey involving 170 workers drawn from Tourism related businesses (resorts, recreation centers, museums and parks) in Port Harcourt from the period between October 2013 – July 2014. The study units were individual organizational members, and the micro-level of analysis was adopted. The population of the study was 400 employees consisting of: front-desk officers, housekeepers, chefs, bar attendants, cooks, potters, workers in travel agencies and recreation parks in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. A sample size of 196 was determined using Krejcie and Morgan (1970), adopted by Sekaran (2003). Cluster sampling technique was adopted to select the sample elements from the population. From the 196 copies of the questionnaire distributed and retrieved, only 170 were found usable for the study. The 170 copies represent 86.73 percent of the 196. Thus, 170 was taken as the sample worked in this study.

Affective commitment was measured with a 16-item instrument (that reflects on its four core aspects) developed from Meyer et al (1993) 6-item instrument. Ingratiation was measured with a 3-item instrument. The Likert type scale ranging from: Strongly disagree, Disagree, Undecided, Agree, to Strongly agree. These were used to indicate agreement on each of the items. The instrument validity was achieved through professional agreement, while the reliability was achieved through Cronbatch Alpha test. In this test, we recorded a minimum of 0.8 point which is higher than Nunally's (1978) recommended benchmark of 0.70.

The questionnaire instrument was used to survey the subordinates on their managers/supervisors' ingratiation and their self-affective commitment. This method favours Polychroniou (2009); Kerr et al (2006); Rahim et al 2006 in Polychroniou (2009); Dodd and Brown (2011); Okaomee (2011) and Goleman (2000), where it is argued that there is always inaccuracies of responses gotten when managers are asked to rate themselves. It is shown in those arguments that ineffective managers overestimate their skills compared to effective managers.

Analysis and Findings

The demographic and univariate analysis were done using descriptive statistical tools. Demographic factors considered were gender and educational qualification. Amongst the 170 workers, 10% have BSc/HND, 15% OND/NCE, 55% have WASC/GCE and 20% have professional certificates.

The result of the univariate analysis is shows in Table 1: the mean score obtained for managers ingratiation is 2.88. The results show a moderate use of affection to attract likeability. Workers’ selfless interest has a mean score of 3.26, which shows a higher level of interest in their job. Also, workers dedication to their job has the mean score of 2.61, which indicates a favourable sense of duty and responsibility. Worker’s sense of belongingness has the mean of 3.16, indicating a very strong association and feeling of attachment workers have with the organizations where they work. The mean score of civic virtue (3.33) indicates a favourable existence of organizational citizen behavior amongst workers at work. **Table 1: Descriptive Analysis of Study Variables**

	N	MEAN	STD.DEV	SKEWNESS	
	Stat	Stat	Stat	Statistic std. error	
Ingratiation	170	2.88	1.10393	-.250	.752
Selfless interest	170	3.26	.92744	-.372	.309
Dedication to job	170	2.61	.81156	.093	.309
Belongingness	170	3.16	.83642	0.35	.309
Civic virtue	170	1.84	1.962	1.096	.701

Table 2: Spearman’s Correlation between Ingratiation and Affective Commitment

			Selfawareness	Selfless Interest	Dedicatio n to Job	Belongingn ess	Civic Virtue
Spearman’s Correlation rho	Self-awareness	1	1.000	.425**	.328**	.337**	.171*
Coefficient (Sig. tailed)		(2-	.000	.000	.000	.000	.025
N		170	170	170	170	170	170
Selfless Correlation	Interest	1	.425**	1.000	.538**	.437**	.211**
Coefficient (Sig. tailed)		(2-	.000	.000	.000	.000	.006
N		170	170	170	170	170	170
Dedication Correlation	to Job	1	.328**	.538**	1.000	.351**	.328**
Coefficient (Sig. tailed)		(2-	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
N		170	170	170	170	170	170

Belongingness Correlation	1 (2-	.337**	.437**	.351**	1.000	.273**
Coefficient Sig. tailed)		.000	.000	.000		.000
N		170	170	170	170	170
Civic Virtue 1 Correlation		.171**	.211**	.328**	.273**	1.000
Coefficient Sig. (2tailed)		.025	.006	.000	.000	
N		170	170	170	170	170

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

The result shows that ingratiation is positively associated with selfless-interest ($r = .425$; $P < 0.01$); ingratiation is also positively associated with dedication to job ($r = .328$; $P > 0.01$); the association between ingratiation and sense of belonging is ($r = .337$; $P > 0.01$); and the correlation between ingratiation and civic virtue ($r = .171$; $P > 0.01$). The Spearman’s correlation coefficient (r) in Ho1, Ho2 and Ho3 show definite and strong positive association between ingratiation and selfless interest, dedication to job and sense of belonging. Their coefficient is greater than .2, therefore we reject hypotheses 1, 2 and 3. On the contrary, the r value of hypothesis Ho4 is $r = .171$; ($P < .2$), therefore, we accept the hypotheses. This indicates a positive but very weak (insignificant) association between ingratiation and civic virtue. **Fig. 1: A Heuristic Model on Ingratiation and Affective Commitment in Tourism Based Businesses**

Based Businesses

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

The focus of the study was to investigate the association between ingratiation and affective commitment. The result shows that ingratiation is positively and strongly associated with selfless-interest, dedication to job and sense of belonging; but weakly associated with civic virtue.

The positive and very strong association between ingratiation and measures of affective commitment, except civic virtue is predicated on the fact established in the study that ingratiation is driven by goals, motivation and largely determined by time, place and nature of the relationship. This study being on a downward impression management, it is possible the presenter (managers) often succeeds in use of flattering and other self-presentation strategies to elicit commitment (Emmanuel, 2012; and Okaomee, 2011).

The forging argument on our findings is also supported by the contention that, where the managers' power capacity generates adequate incentive value, on an accurate subjective probability, with perceived legitimacy, ingratiation produces emotional commitment. These were quite obvious in our interactions with the managers; particularly, most managers admitted using flattering and gift-giving to present positive self to subordinates. Another facet supportive of our findings is the argument that subordinates tend to be loyal and emotionally committed to leaders who exhibit sufficient referent power (Robins and Sanghi, 2006). Ingratiation is a strong attribute and manifestation of referent power at work.

However, the weak association between ingratiation and civic virtue tends to confirm the validity in the logic of those who contend against impression management. For instance, critique of Goffman on impression management argued that his theory tends to reduce society to –episodic interaction rather than addressing broader phenomena that serve to maintain social inequality (Chris, 2003). Goffman's (1958 in Emmanuel, 2012) model is seen as hopelessly cynical and limited in assessment of human beings. In some sense, it is the view of such critics that impression management puts on the kind of performance that deceives both self and other (Roynolds, 1987 in Emmanuel 2012) therefore, apathetic to human suffering.

Given all these, it is perhaps possible that workers may perceive the un-enduring realities portrayed in ingratiation as lacking in any tangible value than emotional therapy. If this be the case, then, the civic responsibility and duty of the workers will be negatively affective or reduced as ingratiation does not transcend the psychological gains of the individual to his economic wellbeing. For instance, the workers interviewed largely complained about their salaries being less than the minimum wage, in the context of a workplace that depicts affluence.

In figure 1, the heuristic model on ingratiation and affective commitment in tourism-based business was drawn from the findings and conclusion derived from the study. It is demonstrated that managers' ingratiation has strong influence on the workers' sense of affective commitment, but this is directly through the workers' demonstration of selfless interest, dedication and sense of belonging. However, managers' ingratiation has weak influence on civic virtue which also translates to a weak impact on workers' affective commitment.

Based on this, we conclude that ingratiation highly associates or influences affective commitment, but very temporarily, because it is directed at the emotional wellbeing, devoid of any profound rational judgment and cognitive value. The fact that the things of human emotion do not last, implies that ingratiation is only an episodic credit balance in the psychological account of the workers which translates to nothing in the economic realities of the individual. Unfortunately, it is the economic reality that determines man's consciousness and rationality. The analysis was based on conceptualized relationship between managers' ingratiation and affective commitment. On ingratiation, respondents were asked to rank the extent to which, their manager were presented to use flattery, project self-image,

inspiring words as they demonstrate self-awareness and presentation to motivate subordinate in their interactions at work. On affective commitment, respondents were asked to rank their opinion on the extent to which they feel satisfied and found their work interesting and rewarding and the extent to which they sacrifice personal comfort for firm benefit (self-less interest); sense of integration, and willingness to seek other opportunities outside the firm and feeling of fairness (sense of belonging); attention and time given to duty and responsibilities (dedication to job); and concern for general or public interest within the firm (civic virtue). The areas considered were interpersonal relationship with colleagues and managers, concern for firm's facilities, long term survival, and identification with firm's public image.

Drawing from our conclusion and the givens on the heuristic model, the implications are that the managers self-presentation in terms of strategic self-disclosure, flattery and use of inspiring words are impressions perceived in positive light by the subordinate who naturally sees his boss as a role model. This relationship is gainful sustained when the managers have the self-awareness to use ingratiation as a tool to elicit affective commitment. His impressions inspire and motivate the worker as long as the manager maintains ingratiation influence over the worker who finds a lively relationship at the workplace. However, the weak civic virtue can be strengthened where the manager compliments ingratiation with exemplification to neutralize the deceit and falsehood perceived in ingratiation.

Our recommendation is that managers seeking to attract their subordinates should combine ingratiation with exemplification, substantial economic value to cultivate, sustain and transit to affective workers' commitment. This is necessary because ingratiation has temporary psychological impact, and a means to an end.

REFERENCES

- Abelson, R.P. (2010), "The Psychological status of the script concept". *American Psychologist*, 36: 715-729.
- Agarwal, S. and Ragaswami, S.N. (1993). –Affective Organizational Commitment of Sales People: An Expanded Model, *Journal of Personal Selling and Sales Management*, Vol. 8, No.2, p.49-70. [Accessed 15 June 2011].
- Allen, N. J., & Meyer, J. P. (1990), –The measurement and antecedents of affective, continuance, and normative commitment to the organization. | *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, 63, 1-18.
- Ali, A., Haq, I.U., Ramay, M.I. and Azeem, M.U. (2010). _The Impact of Psychological Contract on Affective Commitment, *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, Vol. 2, No.7, p. 239-248. Available at: ijcrb.webs.com [Accessed 15 June, 2001].
- Amaral, L.A.N. and B. Uzzi. (2007), –Complex Systems—A New Paradigm for the Integrative Study of Management, Physical, and Technological Systems|. *Management Science*, 53, 7: 1033–1035.
- Arkin, R.M., & Shepherd, J.A. (2010), *Self-Presentation styles in organizations*.
- Asawo, S.P. (2009). Spirituality Leadership and Worker's Commitment in

- Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria. PhD Thesis, Rivers State University of Science and Technology, Port Harcourt.
- Bales, R.F. (2000), *Task status and likeability as a function of talking and listening in decision making Groups*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago.
- Baridam, D.M. and Nwibere, B.M. (2008). *Understanding and Managing Organisational Behaviour*. Sherbrooke Associates, Port Harcourt.
- Barrow S. Mostley R. (2005), *The Employer Brand Bringing: Bringing the Best of Brand Management to People at Work*. England, John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
- Bateman, T. S., & Organ, D. W. (1983). –Job Satisfaction and the Good soldier: The Relationship between Affect and Employee Citizenship. | *Academy of Management Journal*, 26, 587-595.
- Becker, H. S. (2006), –Notes on the Concept of Commitment|. *American Journal of Sociology*, 66, 32-42.
- Biswas, S. (2009). –Affective Commitment as a Mediator between Psychological Climate and Job Involvement|, *Journal of Management & Public Policy*, Vol. 1, No. 1, July-December 2009, p. 22-32. [Accessed 15 June 2011].
- Blau, P. M. (1964), *Exchange and power in social life*. New York: Wiley.
- Borman, W. C., & Motowidlo, S. J. (2010), *Expanding the Criterion Domain to include Elements of Contextual Performance*. New York.
- Brass, D.J., & Burkhardt, M.E. (1993), –Potential Power and Power Use: An Investigation of Structure Behavior. | *Academy of Management Journal*, 34: 141-160.
- Campbell, J.D., & Fehr, B.A. (1990), –Self-esteem and Perceptions of Conveyed Impressions: is Negatively Associated with Greater Realism? | *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 58:122-123.
- Chai-Amonphaisal, K. and Ussahawanitchakit, P. (2008). –Roles of Human Resource Practices and Organisational Justice in Affective Commitment and Job Performance of Accountants in Thai Firms| *Review of Business Research*, Vol. 8, No.2, p.47-58. Available at <http://search.epnet.com>. [Accessed 15 June 2011].
- Christie, R. (I, F. L. (1970) *Studies in Machiavellianism* New York: Academic Press. Cohen, J. (1977), *Statistical Power Analysis for the Behaviour Sciences*. New York: Academic Press.

- Caldwell, D., & O'Reilly, C. (1982). – Responses to Failure: The Effects of Choice and Responsibility on Impression Management. | *Academy of Management Journal*, 25, 1211-36.
- Carno, W.D. (2000), –Milestones in the Psychological Analysis of Social Influence. Group Dynamics: Theory|, *Research and Practice*, 4: 68-80.
- Deconinck, J.B. and Stilwell, C.D. (2004). –Incorporating Organizational Justice, Roles States, Pay Satisfaction and Superior Satisfaction in a Model of Turnover Intentions|. *Journal of Business Research*, Vol. 54, p.225-231. In: Rungruang, P. and Tangchitnob, J.N. (2010). –what Matter Affective Organizational Commitment: A Case of Thai Stateowned Enterprise Employees|, *International Employment Relations Review*, Vol. 16, No. 1, p. 53-68. Available at <http://search.epnet.com>. Accessed 15 June 2011.
- De Gilder D. (2003), –Commitment, Trust and Work Behavior. The Case of Contingent Workers|. *Personal Review*, Vol.32. No.5, pp. 558-606
- Duan, J., Lam, W. Chen, Z. and Zhong, J.A. (2010). –Leadership Justice, Negative Organizational Behaviours and the Mediating Effect of Organizational commitment|, *Social Behaviour and Personality*, Vol. 38, No.9, p. 1289-96. [Accessed 15 June 2011]
- Dunham, R.B., Grube, J.A., & Castafi eda. M.B. (1994). –Organizational Commitment: The utility of an integrative definition|. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 70, 370-380. In: Lu,
- L, Siu, O. and Lu, C. (2010). –Role of Affective Organizational Commitment in the Greater China Region|, *Stress and Health*, Vol. 26, p. 161-168, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. Available at <http://search.epnet.com>. [Accessed 15 June 2011].
- Eisenberger, R., Fasolo, P., & Davis-LaMastrO, V. (1990). –Perceived Organizational Support and Employee Diligence, Commitment, and Innovation|; *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 75, 51-59.
- Eisenberger, R., Huntington, R., Hutchison, S., & Sowa, D. (1986). –Perceived Organizational Support|. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 71, 500-507. Emmanuel, I.E. (2012). –Impression Management and Organizational Commitment in Commercial Banks in Nigeria. | MBA Thesis, University of Port Harcourt. Gandz, J., & Murray, V. V. (1980). –The Experience of Workplace Politics|. *Academy of Management Journal*, 23, 237-251.
- Goleman, D. (2000). –Leadership that Gets Result|. In: *Harvard Business Review*, March- April 2000. Available at: <http://www.hbr.org>
- Grey C. and Garsten C., (2001), *Trust, Control and Post-Bureaucracy*. Sage Publishing
- Heffener,T. (2001), –Organizational commitment and social interaction: A multiple constituencies approach|. *Journal of vocational behavior*, vol.59, no.3, pp. 471-490.

- Jones, E., & Pittman, T. (2009). –Toward a General Theory of Strategic Self Presentation. In J. Suls (Ed.), *Psychological Perspectives on the Self* (pp. 231-262). Kerr, R., Garvin, J., Heaton, N. and Boyle, E. (2006). –Emotional intelligence and management development implications: Insights from the Lebanese context, *Journal of Management Development*, Vol. 27 No.3. Available at: www.emeraldinsight.com. [Accessed 27 December 2010].
- Krejcie, R.V. and Morgan, D.W. (1970). Educational and psychological measurement. 30, 607- 610.
- Koys, D.J. (1991). –Fairness, legal compliance and organizational commitment, *Employee Responsibility and Rights Journal*. Vol. 1, p. 83-291. In:Chai-Amonphasal, K. and
- Ussahawanitchakit, P. (2008). –Roles of Human Resource Practices and Organisational Justice in Affective Commitment and Job Performance of Accountants in Thai Firms, *Review of Business Research*, Vol. 8, No.2, p.47-58. Available at <http://search.epnet.com>. [Accessed 15 June 2011].
- Liden, R. C., & Mitchell, T. R. (2010). –Ingratiation behaviors in organizational settings, *Academy of Management Review*, 13, 572-587.
- Lim, M., Griffiths, G. and Sambrook, S. (2010). Organizational structure for the twenty- first century. Presented at the annual meeting of The Institute for Operations Research and The Management Sciences, Austin.
- Lu, L., Siu, O. and Lu, C. (2010). –Role of Affective Organisational Commitment in the Greater China Region, *Stress and Health*, Vol. 26. P.161-168, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. Available at <http://search.epnet.com>. [Accessed 15 June 2011].
- Malik, O.F., Waheed, A. and Malik, K. (2010). –The Mediating Effect of Job Satisfaction on Role Stressors and Affective Commitment, *International Journal of Business and Management*, Vol. 5, No.11, p.223-235. Available at: www.ccsenet.org/ijbm. [Accessed 15 June 2011].
- Mathieu, J. E., & Zajac, D.M. (2007). –A Review and Meta-analysis of the Antecedents, Correlates, and Consequences of Organizational Commitment. | *Psychological Bulletin*, 108, 171-194.
- McGee, G. W., & Ford, R. C. (2009). –Two (or more) Dimensions of Organizational Commitment: Reexamination of the Affective and Continuance Commitment Scales. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 72, 638-641.
- Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (2007). –Testing the Side-bet Theory of Organizational Commitment: Some Methodological Considerations. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 69, 372-378.
- Mayer, J.P., Stanley, D.J., Herscovitch, L. and Topolnysky, L. (2002). –Affective, Continuance and Normative Commitment to the Organisation: A meta-analysis of Antecedents, Correlates and Consequences, *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, Elsevier Science, USA, Vol. 61, p.20-52. [Accessed 19 July 2011].

- Morrison, T. (2007) Emotional Intelligence, Emotion and Social Work: Context, Characteristics, Complications and Contribution, *British Journal of Social Work*, Vol. 37, p.245-263
- Mowday, R.T., Porter, L.W. and Steers, R.M. (1982). –Employee-Organisation Linkages, *The Psychology of Commitment Absenteeism and Turnover*”, Academic Press, New York, NY. In: Gunlu, E., Aksarayli, M. and Percin, N.S. (2010). –Job satisfaction and organizational commitment of hotel managers in Turkey”, *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Vol. 22 No.5, p.613-717 [Accessed 28 December 2010]
- Okaomee, A.A. (2011) Leadership Emotional Intelligence and Workers’ Affective Commitment: Survey of Commercial Banks in Rivers State. MBA Thesis, University of Port Harcourt.
- Polychroniou, P.V. (2009). –Relationship between emotional intelligence and transformational leadership of supervisors: The impact on team effectiveness”, *Team Performance Management*, Vol. 15 Issue:7/8, p.343-356. [Accessed 26 December 2010].
- Rahim, M.A., Psenicka, C., Polychroniou, P., Oh, S.Y., Ferdausy, S. and Dias, J.F. (2006). –Emotional Intelligence and transformational leadership: a group level analysis in five countries”, *Current Topics in Management*, Vol. 11, Transaction Publishers, Piscataway, NJ, p.223-36. In: Polychroniou, P.V. (2009). –Relationship between emotional intelligence and transformational leadership of supervisors: The impact on team effectiveness”, *Team Performance Management*, Vol. 15 Issue: 7/8, p.343-356. [Accessed 26 December 2010].
- Robins, S.P. and Sanghi, S. (2006). *Organisational Behaviour*, India; Dorling Kindersley Rousseau, V. and Aube, C. (2010). –Social Support at Work and Affective Commitment to the Organisation: The Moderating Effect of Job Resource Adequacy and Ambient Conditions”, *The Journal of Social Psychology*, Vol. 150, No. 4, p.321-340, Taylor & Francis Group, LLC. Available at <http://search.epnet.com>. [Accessed 15 June, 2011]. Rungruang, P. and Tangchitnob, J.N., (2010). –What Mater Affective Organisational Commitment: A Case of Thai State-owned Enterprise Employees”, *International Employment Relations Review*, Vol. 16, No. 1, p.53-68. Available at <http://search.epnet.com>. Accessed 15 June, 2011.
- Sartain, L. & Shuman M. (2006), *Brand from the Inside: Eight essential to Emotionally Connect your Employees to your Business*. Jossey-Bass, San Francisco.
- Sekaran, U. (2003). *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*, 4th Edition
- Sullivan, J. (2004), –Eight Element of a Successful Employment brand”, ER daily, February, 23 Available at www.erechangc.com/i/c,rticis/db/
- Whitehead, A.N. (1958) *Dialogues of Alfred North Whitehead* (Recorded by L. Price) Boston: Little, Brown and Company.

Zorlu, K. (2010). –Effect of Human Capital Elements on Organisational Commitment in Businesses and a Study in the Banking Sector in Kirsehir Provincell, Journal of World of Turks, Vol. 2, No.3, p.107-b130. [Accessed 18 January 2011].